

Passive Intermodulation Measurements on Human Skin and Tissue “in vivo” around 800 MHz

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There have been several discussions in the past about possible faint nonlinearities of human skin and tissue also in the context of better understanding possible nonthermal effects (demodulation of the pulsed carrier) with subsequent faint signals at low frequencies in the brain. It is very well known that the skin has, at low frequencies a rather non linear resistance and impedance and a resistance. This is in particular relevant for safety considerations, since in the low frequency range (50 Hz) the resistance very significantly decreases above, say 50 Volt applied. In the high frequency range this nonlinearity is much less pronounced and there are papers claiming that in the GHz range is unmeasurably small [1]. Here we show a very simple setup, using a commercial PIM (Passive intermodulation test instrument) which carefully selected setting (2x2 Watt and a duty cycle of 1 %) to avoid significant heating as well as peak voltages beyond 40 Volt on the DUT (e.g. here a finger of one of the authors) as evident from Fig 1.

The situation is self explaining and does not require a lot of detailed additional explanation:

Fig. 1a

Measurements result from a simple PIM test around 750 MHz on the finger of a volunteer; when the finger is touching the output connector of the instrument, the IP3 signal goes up by 30..40 dB. Note that the IP3 method is using two RF carriers (here 734 MHz and 757 MHz respectively) operating in a low duty cycle mode.

Fig .1b

Photograph of the device under test.

The practical consequence of this very simple test is a non destructive measurement method for such faint nonlinearities near 1GHz which can be applied in vivo (certain safety rules to be respected) . One may try to calculate the amount of “demodulated “ signal in the low frequency range which otherwise is not easily measurable directly. In particular the results shown here are in sharp contrast to the claim [1] that bio-tissue has no measurable EM nonlinearity in the range around 1 GHz.

On the other hand one may speculate about possible diagnostic applications (certain tissue and skin parameters which may otherwise not easily accessible) in the medical sector, since this technique has barely (if any) been used so far.

LIMITATIONS OF RF BIORESEARCH

Using Ultra-Sensitive Techniques to Search for Nonlinear Effects

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Reference [1]

This paper used a second harmonic generation technique in the same microwave cavity.

RESULTS AND IMPLICATION

**LIVING TISSUES TESTED HAVE NO DETECTABLE
ELECTRIC OR MAGNETIC NONLINEARITY
AT 800 MHz**

- **NO COHERENT DETECTION AT THE MEMBRANE**
- **NO DOUBLE PHOTON ABSORPTION**
- **NO SECOND HARMONIC GENERATION FROM CHIRAL MOLECULES**
- **NO MAGNETIC NONLINEARITY**

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The authors would also like to mention a recent discussion related to the subject on research gate

<https://www.researchgate.net/messages/47810522>